

A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis, and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions

D8.1 CVDLINK raising awareness and dissemination plan

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Project Summary

In the EU, more than 6 million new cardiovascular disease (CVD) cases and 1.8 million deaths are reported yearly, imposing a substantial burden on national healthcare systems and society in general. The development of effective preventive interventions, adopted for each individual and population, will reduce the overall cost of patient management and justify the assertion that CVDs can be prevented and controlled. The exploration of existing clinical, genetic, and real-world data sources can contribute to these goals. However, several challenges related to data availability, management, and processing complicate this process. The 48-month CVDLINK project aims to tackle these challenges by implementing a privacy-by-design European-wide federated platform-as-a-service (PaaS) to deliver effective data-driven human-centric interventions and advance research and management in the CVD domain. CVDLINK is based on two major offerings: (1) the seamless and legally compliant integration, secure sharing, and automated curation of existing data, and (2) a set of AI and data-enabled precision medicine tools and pipelines for better diagnosis, risk stratification, and treatment of CVDs. The project will examine seven different cardiovascular conditions, making use of retrospective datasets, cohort studies, and biobanks from seven countries, aiming to demonstrate how heterogeneous data sources can be effectively exploited to build comprehensive AI-driven tools to benefit health systems, patients, industry, and EU citizens. The developed tools will be validated in five countries, demonstrating the impact of the CVDLINK outputs. Additionally, the project will generate a set of best practices which, alongside a cost-effectiveness analysis and awareness-raising campaigns, will promote the adoption of CVDLINK outputs in the mid-term.

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Executive Summary

The following deliverable outlines the CVDLINK project's dissemination and communication strategy, which focuses on maximising the project's impact by raising awareness and ensuring results are widely available to target audiences.

The document includes the project's approach to dissemination and communication, presents the project's visual identity, and identifies target audiences, communication channels, strategies to raise awareness about the project, and approaches to monitoring these activities.

This deliverable presents a strategy to raise awareness and facilitate the dissemination and communication of the project's objectives, activities, and results, both as a Consortium and as individual partners. Distinct strategies are defined for dissemination and communication activities. The deliverable also defines a timeline for activities, presents partners' preliminary individual dissemination and communication plans, and outlines partners' responsibilities regarding dissemination and communication, which include properly acknowledging EU funding and contributing to activities such as blog writing.

This strategy establishes performance indicators and intermediary targets to monitor and evaluate the efficacy of the proposed approaches. These targets will be evaluated at the midterm point of the project, when the deliverable is updated.

This document establishes the basis for the forthcoming dissemination and communication activities within CVDLINK project.

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List of partners

Abbreviation	Definition
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision SRL
VICOM	Vicomtech
TAU	Tampereen Korkeakoulusaatio Sr
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
TAUH	Pirkanmaan Hyvintialue / Tampere University Hospital
TRI IE	Trilateral Research Limited
TUDa	Technische Universitat Darmstadt
VER	Veracell Oy
AMC	Iatriko Athinon Emporiki Anonymos Etaireia
CERTH	Center For Research and Technology Hellas
HYMC	Hillel Yaffe Medical Center
KIHDL	Kineret Israel Health Data Lake
UHAM	Universitat Hamburg
UMFCD	Carol Davila University of Medicine and Pharmacy Romania
IMSP	Imsp Institute of Cardiology Moldova
WCS	Wellics Efarmoges Erevnas & Pliroforikis Monoprosopi Ike
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
UTARTU	University of Tartu
SYNYO	SYNYO GmbH

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
KPI	Key performance indicator
DCM	Dissemination and communication manager (WP8 lead)
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
AI	Artificial intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EC	European Commission
ICT	Information communication technologies
ELSI	Ethical, legal, and societal impact
RTAI	Responsible, trustworthy AI
GA	Grant Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EHDS	European Health Data Space
1+MG	1+ Million Genomes
PaaS	Platform as a Service
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
DG JUST	Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
End users	People who will use the project results in their work
Stakeholders	Groups with an interest in the project activities and results, including but not limited to end users

Glossary of terms

Term	Definition
Dissemination	Sharing project results to ensure they are available to all stakeholders.
Communication	Sharing project information, including objectives, activities, updates, and milestones, with stakeholder audiences. Unlike dissemination, this is not focused on results exclusively.
Explainability	Refers to the extent to which the internal mechanics of a deep learning model or AI framework can be understood by humans and involves making the operations and outcomes of AI models transparent.
Responsible, Trustworthy AI	AI systems created to prioritise ethical principles, such as explainability, accountability, security, and non-maleficence, to enable human oversight, transparency, data protection, and privacy in the design, development, and deployment.
FAIRification	Process of transforming data to adhere to the FAIR principles, which ensure data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
Privacy-by-design	An approach to building technology and systems that considers and integrates privacy and data protection from the start of development.
Federated storage	Any storage system that integrates and manages multiple, autonomous storage systems as a unified, centrally managed resource.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project vision

CVDLINK aims to reduce the burden of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) by harnessing clinical, genetic, and real-world data sources to better predict, treat, and manage CVDs. The project's primary objective is to create a privacy-by-design federated Platform as a Service (PaaS) which will integrate and securely share data from existing datasets, such as those collated by hospitals and researchers, to deliver data-driven, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered medical tools to healthcare professionals for use in the diagnosis, risk stratification, and treatment of CVDs.

CVDLINK's main objectives are to:

- Analyse the gaps in current approaches to managing CVDs
- Identify challenges in the current data landscape
- Integrate real-world data sources in a FAIR repository
- Implement data-driven AI federated tools to aid the management of CVDs
- Set a paradigm in the use of available data sources
- Conduct validation studies to verify the project tools and test the project's federated storage and learning system
- Contribute to a broader adoption of data and AI-driven approaches to CVD care and healthcare
- Engage with stakeholders to encourage the exploitation of CVDLINK results

1.2 Deliverable scope and objectives

The purpose of this deliverable is to outline the strategies shaping the project's dissemination and communication activities, which aim to create impact by engaging with stakeholders and ensuring CVDLINK activities and results are shared with target audiences. The document defines strategies to maximise the impact of dissemination and communication activities, including timing, target audiences, and key channels, as well as management efforts to ensure activities are consistent and effective. This deliverable will be updated in M24, at which point the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and outlined approaches will be evaluated and amended if necessary.

1.3 Structure of the report

This deliverable summarises a strategy to achieve CVDLINK's dissemination and communication objectives, distinguishing between dissemination and communication. Dissemination refers to the promotion of project results, whereas communication refers to sharing information about all project activities and objectives. As such, this deliverable outlines separate dissemination and communication strategies, while keeping in mind that in many cases the activities and target audiences for these strategies overlap.

Chapter 2 covers the CVDLINK dissemination strategy, including objectives, target audiences, key messages, and channels. Chapter 3 covers the communication strategy, including target audiences, channels, and key messages. Chapter 4 covers management of the dissemination and communication strategies, including the visual identity guidelines, partners' responsibilities, consortium-wide policies, and the timing of activities. Chapter 5 covers potential barriers to dissemination and communication and mitigation strategies, while Chapter 6 covers evaluation and monitoring. The annexes include a variety of resources, including lists of target events and journals, monitoring sheets, the legitimate interest assessment form, and individual partners' dissemination and communication plans.

2 Dissemination strategy

2.1 Objectives

The success of CVDLINK largely relies on the engagement of stakeholders and end users who may adopt the project's tools, participate in data sharing, and engage in conversations about the safe and ethical use of AI in healthcare. As such, the dissemination strategy aims to identify and organise the necessary activities to maximise the dissemination of knowledge generated by the project. If successful, these activities will contribute to exploitation by maximising the uptake of CVDLINK results. The strategy focuses on two main approaches:

- Disseminating the project results to key stakeholders, the European Commission (EC), and the general media
- Enhancing the uptake of project tools and outcomes among healthcare professionals

CVDLINK will combine traditional approaches to dissemination, such as scientific publications and conferences, with interactive and online approaches, such as the project website, hackathons, and clustering workshops.

2.2 Strategy

Dissemination and communication activities will be conducted in four phases, extending beyond the project's end date. Broadly speaking, the phases begin with the creation of an online presence and move towards cultivating first a general awareness of the project's objectives towards a more targeted awareness about the specific benefits the outputs can deliver to different stakeholder groups. The final phase will focus on the exploitation and uptake of the final results.

The phases are summarised as follows:

1. Launch (M01-M06): the project's brand and online presence are established. These will be used as a springboard through which the project will engage end users and facilitate co-creation activities.
2. Growth (M07-M42): the growth phase spans the majority of the project's duration, and as such includes a number of elements. These include creating synergies with other EU and national initiatives via clustering work, publishing results in conferences and peer-reviewed journals, gathering feedback from stakeholders to maximise the project's effectiveness, engaging with general and specialist media, and exploiting online channels to create a basis of interested stakeholders.
3. Conclusion (M43-M48): In addition to promoting the final outputs, during the closing phase of the project partners will participate in clustering activities and workshops to exchange best practices and lessons learnt with stakeholders, while disseminating the benefits of CVDLINK's tools.

4. Post-project: Following the completion of CVDLINK, partners are expected to continue to promote the project and its results through their individual networks. At the same time, the pool of stakeholders cultivated in the earlier phases will continue to exploit and disseminate project outcomes. Further, publications in scientific journals based on the project's results will continue after the end of the project.

Figure 1. Phases of dissemination

CVDLINK will undertake a variety of approaches to dissemination, including:

1. Online dissemination
 - a. Website: the consortium has set up a project website, outlined in D1.5 and available at <https://cvdlink-project.eu>, to serve as a central repository for the project's findings, outputs, and public deliverables. The website will be actively updated throughout the project's duration and maintained for a period of 2 years after the project ends. See Section 2.5.1 for more detail.
 - b. Social media: the consortium will use LinkedIn and YouTube to disseminate important findings and outputs to an online network of target audiences. See Section 3.2.2 for more details.
 - c. Newsletters: the consortium will publish biannual newsletters. At the beginning of the project, these will function more as a communication tool, providing broad information about the project. However, once results become available, newsletters will be an important tool to disseminate these findings to the project's network of stakeholders. See Section 2.5.2 for more details.
 - d. Scientific publications: The goal of these publications is to facilitate knowledge transfer and promotion, contribute to the exploitation of the project's results, and encourage the involvement of interested parties. See Section 2.5.3 for more details.
 - e. Other articles: this includes trade publications targeting mainly experts and professionals, as well as more general media outlets. Like scientific publications, the goal of these articles is to promote the project's results and contribute to the uptake of results. See Section 2.5.3 for more details.
2. Non-electronic dissemination

- a. Brochures and printed materials: these materials will serve to disseminate findings and can be distributed at in-person events and workshops. Note that these will also be available online and distributed in electronic format as much as possible to minimize the project's environmental footprint. See Section 3.2.4 for more details.
3. Interactive dissemination
 - a. This includes academic conferences, cluster workshops, hackathons, and trade fairs and exhibitions. This range of activities will reach different target audiences and disseminate project findings across academic, commercial, and research-oriented events. See Sections 2.5.3 and 2.5.5 for more detail.

Note that some of these channels, particularly the electronic ones, will also be used for communication activities. These approaches will be explained in more detail in Chapter 3.

2.3 Key target audiences

Stakeholder engagement is crucial to the project's success, and the efficacy of achieving impact through dissemination and communication relies on identifying the most relevant stakeholders to target. This also contributes to exploitation, as engaging with groups who will benefit from our findings makes it more likely the results will be used beyond the project's end date.

CVDLINK's key target audiences include:

- Healthcare sector: cardiologists, primary carers, technicians, administrative personnel, directors, and real-world data source providers
- Research stakeholders: cardiology researchers, developers of AI health tools, and biotechnologists
- Citizens and CVD patients
- Civil society: patient organisations, healthcare professional organisations, health research associations, and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)
- Industry and economic stakeholders: industrial actors, technology solutions and service providers, start-ups, and investors
- Public policymakers: EU policymakers, national regulators and agencies
- Initiatives and projects: relevant EU or national projects, European associations, and initiatives such as European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), European Health Data Space (EHDS), and 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG)

The CVDLINK consortium is comprised of partners from across the medical, research, and AI development field, many of which already have connections with stakeholder institutions. The table in Annex 9.2 lists some stakeholder organisations we may target through dissemination activities, including some organisations partners already have connections to.

2.3.1 Building a network

Networking with communities, networks, and associations: Networking and stakeholder engagement will occur across the target audiences within and, in some cases, beyond the EU. These activities will support the overall objectives of dissemination by contributing to the impact and exploitation of the project's outputs. They will also contribute to the project's other goals, including: (1) engaging stakeholders in co-creation activities (which occur under WP2) to contribute expertise and ensure outputs meet the needs of patients and end users, (2) connecting with institutions who may share data with CVDLINK or similar data-driven initiatives, (3) increasing public trust in medical AI tools by engaging in dialogue and demonstrating the ethical, legal, and privacy-protecting elements of the project, (4) facilitating data sharing to support medical innovation beyond the project, and (5) integrating with external infrastructure, such as data providers and tools to support FAIRification, to support exploitation.

Building a contact list: To capitalise on partners' existing networks and relationships and build a contact list that will support the project's dissemination and communication goals, partners will provide a list of stakeholders from their networks, including media. We will either use email addresses that have been given to partners directly by the stakeholders themselves (which implies their consent to be contacted at that email address) or publicly available organisational email addresses. Alongside this collaborative contact list-building, the dissemination and communication manager (DCM, Trilateral Research) will build the list by gathering publicly available contacts from stakeholder organisations and encouraging stakeholders to sign up to the newsletter via social media and the website.

The personal information collected in CVDLINK's contact list will be managed according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016):

- On the basis of informed consent (GDPR Art. 6.1.a):
 - People subscribed to the CVDLINK newsletter through the project website
 - People who have expressed interest in the CVDLINK project (e.g., participation in workshops, contact with individual partners, etc.)
- On the basis of legitimate interest (GDPR Art. 6.1.f):
 - Based on legitimate interest, project information and updates can be shared with contacts working in fields related to the CVDLINK project. These contacts must only include professional emails that are publicly available online, and contacts will always be given the option to unsubscribe from further communications in conformity with the GDPR.

A legitimate interest assessment form has been developed and was confirmed with the Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers (DG JUST) at the EC as a lawful basis that can be used to build stakeholder lists within EU projects. The assessment form is available to all partners on the project's SharePoint and is attached to this deliverable in Annex 9.7.

On the basis of this assessment form, CVDLINK will adhere to the following process:

- Collect relevant business contacts (i.e., organisational emails, as opposed to personal ones)
- Always include the option to opt-out from any further communications
- The project's Privacy Policy will specify how CVDLINK uses contacts and confirms that contacts will be used only for the purposes of the project.

Collaboration with other EC-funded projects: CVDLINK will connect with other EC-funded projects that focus on relevant topics (such as cardiovascular care, medical AI, health data, etc.). Projects can exchange knowledge and benefit from sharing each other's audiences. Under Task 8.3, CVDLINK will organise two clustering events and workshops to facilitate these activities.

Collaboration with other initiatives and infrastructures: CVDLINK aims to integrate with existing initiatives to ensure the sustainability of project results. As part of these efforts, the project will network with initiatives linked to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), European Health Data Space (EHDS), and 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG).

2.4 Key messages

Dissemination material will share results with the maximum amount of stakeholders throughout Europe and beyond, such as healthcare professionals, technology developers, and patient organisations. Because the project aims to reach a diverse range of target audiences, it's critical to consider how messaging can be structured to reach distinct groups, considering elements such as which messages to deliver, what channels to use, and the wording and tone. For example, messages delivered to citizen groups should use much less technical language and jargon than messaging directed to academics.

Considering the importance of producing effective material throughout dissemination activities, we will consider three main pillars when publishing content:

1. Awareness. Some target audiences may derive benefits from learning about the project's activities and outputs, but don't require in-depth, technical information. With these groups in mind, we will create awareness messages about CVDLINK's work to develop a recognisable identity for the project.
2. Understanding. Other audiences must be targeted directly, because they can benefit from CVDLINK's outputs as potential end users. For these groups, we will produce content designed to nurture their understanding of the project's work.
3. Commitment and Action. Any audiences in a position to adopt some of the CVDLINK's outputs will be identified and targeted with specially developed content.

A major effort underlying the CVDLINK dissemination and communication activities will focus on sharing evidence of the safety, efficacy, and trustworthiness of data sharing and medical AI solutions. As such, particular attention will be paid to project activities related to ELSI (ethical, legal, and socially important) data sharing practices, RTAI (responsible,

trustworthy AI) principles such as transparency, explainability, and bias mitigation, and the safe implementation of AI tools into medical practice.

The table below presents CVDLINK's preliminary key stakeholder groups identified in the Grant Agreement (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023), tailored key messages for each, and the channels used to deliver them. This may be updated throughout the duration of the project.

Target group	Key messages	Targeted channels	General channels
Healthcare sector	Focus on data sharing capabilities and security, privacy, and trust promotion	Workshops, interviews, demonstrations of CVDLINK tools and data sharing functionalities	CVDLINK website, social media, newsletters, promotional material, clustering activities
Research stakeholders	Demonstrate new abilities to build and train novel tools		
Citizens and patients	The benefits and trustworthiness of personalised diagnostic and prevention services	CVDLINK co-creation approach (workshops, online campaigns)	
Civil society	Public awareness and promotion of a data sharing culture and better health outcomes	Workshops, interviews, co-creation activities	
Industry and economic stakeholders	The creation of new AI-driven applications alongside open access to project results and data for building future novel tools		
Policymakers	The development and implementation of cost-effective and sustainable CVD interventions with the potential to	Demonstration of CVDLINK tools and data sharing functionalities	

	decrease human and economic costs of CVDs and free up healthcare system capacity		
Initiatives and projects	Facilitating knowledge exchange, producing FAIRified datasets, and sharing research outcomes	Synergies, joint activities, workshops	

Table 1. Target audiences and key messages

2.5 Dissemination channels and tools

2.5.1 Project website

The project website (<https://cvdlink-project.eu>) is the main online tool for public dissemination. Many other dissemination activities, such as blogs and public deliverables, will be launched from and stored on the website; as such, it functions as the central repository for the project. Its structure will enable the consortium to tailor messages to distinct target audiences throughout the duration of the project.

The project website was launched in M06 (June 2024) and is managed by Trilateral Research (see D1.5 for greater detail about the website's layout and contents). The website will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration. At publication, the website features an "About" page, introducing the project's objectives and defining key concepts, a "Project Outcomes" page, breaking down the work packages in non-technical language, a "News" page, where blogs and press releases will be posted, and a "Consortium" page with information about each partner.

We anticipate adding the following pages throughout the project's duration:

- A publications page, with sections for public deliverables, journal articles, and other publications
- A page for end users, previewing the outputs that will be useable in industry, and which will be updated as project outputs are finalised

The website will direct users to other channels, including the project's social media page and newsletter.

Newsletters, blogs, and other project outcomes will be posted on the website as they become available to ensure the website is an up-to-date source of information. Website updates will be promoted on social media, creating a symbiotic relationship in which different channels are used to promote and drive engagement with each other. Partners

will be asked to regularly contribute blogs, which will be published monthly in the “News” section (for more on blogs, see Section 3.2.8), and to promote them within their networks. These should drive website traffic while enhancing opportunities for networking, collaboration, and exploitation. The number of website visitors will be monitored throughout the lifetime of the project to evaluate the efficacy of the dissemination strategy. Trilateral will maintain the project website for at least two years after the end date of the project, to ensure CVDLINK and its results remain visible and in the public domain.

Figure 2. Website landing page

2.5.2 Newsletters

Starting in M07 (July 2024), CVDLINK will produce a newsletter to be released every six months. The newsletters will contain news about upcoming project activities and events and link to blogs on the project website, project publications as they become available, and interesting articles from external sources on related topics.

The newsletters will be designed in accordance with CVDLINK’s visual identity, using the project colour and logo. The first newsletter will focus on the launch of the project and the activities of the first six months, including the kick-off and first plenary meetings.

The newsletters will be designed and distributed using [Zoho](#), a GDPR compliant platform used by Trilateral for several other projects. We will create a mailing list on Zoho based on the project’s stakeholder and media list, which are updated on a regular basis. Thus, recipients of the newsletter will include those we believe may have a legitimate interest in receiving updates about the topics related to the project, as well as those who have signed up for the newsletter via the website or other means (i.e., informed consent). Once distributed, newsletters will be published on the website and shared on social media to generate wider impact.

2.5.3 Scientific dissemination

Partners will achieve scientific dissemination through academic journal articles and participation in academic conferences, industry expos, and networking events. This phase of dissemination will pick up once project results become available, although earlier scientific dissemination is possible through presentations and articles explaining the theoretical underpinnings, methodology, or novel ambitions of the project. Journals and conferences will be selected based on their impact factor and influence within the relevant disciplines.

The Dissemination and Communication Manager (DCM, Trilateral Research) will facilitate these activities by keeping an updated repository of event and publication opportunities in the project's SharePoint. The repository was created in M2 and will be updated on an ongoing basis. Partners will be informed of upcoming deadlines at monthly plenary meetings, WP8 meetings, and via email bulletins.

Journal opportunities

Examples of scientific journals are listed below:

- Artificial Intelligence in Medicine (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/artificial-intelligence-in-medicine>)
- European Heart Journal (<https://academic.oup.com/eurheartj>)
- BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making (<https://bmcmedinformdecismak.biomedcentral.com/>)
- Ethics, Medicine and Public Health (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/ethics-medicine-and-public-health>)

For a longer list of journals, see Annex 9.3.

Conferences and events

Partners will attend events, conferences, and seminars to disseminate findings. The CVDLINK project will also host three co-creation workshops to collate feedback and collaboratively problem solve with experts under WP2 and will host two events alongside smaller workshops with affiliated projects under T8.3.

Examples of conferences are listed below:

- GAIA-X Health Data Space Event (<https://gaia-x.eu/>)
- European Public Health Conference (<https://ephconference.eu/>)
- MICCAI – Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Interventions (<https://miccai.org/>)
- AIME – International Conference of AI in Medicine (<https://aime24.aimeinfo.info/>)

For a longer list of events, see Annex 9.4.

2.5.4 Collaboration with other EU projects

Collaboration with sister projects occurs under T8.3, which is led by SIMAVI and begins in M13. The development of synergies with similar projects will contribute to the sustainability of project results and boost dissemination efforts. This task will identify relevant projects and liaise with them to pursue opportunities for joint events and publications, alongside communications initiatives introducing the cluster members to each project's respective audiences.

We plan to organise two cluster events as well as smaller workshops, where cluster members can exchange knowledge and plan joint activities. These workshops and events will contribute to the dissemination and exploitation of CVDLINK results by sister projects, enable networking with target stakeholders, and provide the opportunity to learn from other projects. Whenever possible, and considering issues such as confidentiality, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, and data protection, we will exchange data, tools, methods, knowledge, and other project resources.

Below is a list of projects related to CVDLINK that the consortium aims to connect with under T8.3.

Project title and acronym	Information
INCISIVE (https://incisive-project.eu/): A multimodal AI-based toolbox and an interoperable health imaging repository for the empowerment of imaging analysis related to the diagnosis, prediction, and follow-up of cancer	Focused on improving cancer diagnosis and prediction by creating an AI and data-driven set of tools to improve imaging analysis. Uses similar architecture, federated storage, and DevOps as CVDLINK. AUTH is a partner.
MES-CoBraD (https://www.mes-cobrad.eu/): The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders	Aims to improve diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in patients with Complex Brain Disorders using real-world data from multiple clinical and consumer sources.
PerCard (https://projects.tuni.fi/percard/about/): Personalised Prognostics and Diagnostics for Improved Decision Support in Cardiovascular Diseases	Applies novel analysis methods (AI, machine learning, signal processing) to different data sources to improve risk modelling for cardiovascular disease. TAU is a partner.
FeatureCloud (https://featurecloud.eu/)	Creates a federated, decentralised AI platform with maximum privacy safeguards for sensitive datasets. UHAM is a partner.

AEGLE (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/644906): An analytics framework for integrated and personalized healthcare services in Europe	Develops a European platform for big data analytics in healthcare. AUTH is a partner.
DIGITAL EUCAIM (https://www.egi.eu/project/eucaim/): European Cancer Imaging Initiative	Will establish a federated infrastructure of anonymized, FAIRified cancer images and a platform for development of AI tools for cancer diagnosis and treatment. AUTH is a partner.
HOSMARTAI (https://www.hosmartai.eu/): Hospital Smart development based on AI	Creates an open platform with tools to facilitate the development and integration of robotics and AI technologies into healthcare systems.
iToBoS (https://itobos.eu): Intelligent Total Body Scanner for Early Detection of Melanoma	Creates an AI-powered body scanner to aid in the early diagnosis of melanoma, integrating data sources including medical records and genomics. TRI is a partner.

Table 2. Other projects for potential collaborations

2.5.5 Project events

Partners are planning to coordinate several events, including consultation interviews, information sessions, and brokerage events. The consortium will coordinate three hackathons for building new tools utilizing CVDLINK data sharing innovations, alongside the cluster events and co-creation workshops mentioned in previous sections.

2.5.6 Zenodo

All public deliverables will be published on [Zenodo](#). Zenodo is an open repository developed by the European [OpenAIRE](#) program, which allows researchers to publish papers, datasets, and other digital material. Zenodo tracks how many views each item has, making it a useful tool for monitoring project impact.

Rather than uploading these items to the website as a PDF, they will be added to the website as citations which link to the Zenodo page (Figure 3). Because Zenodo tracks the number of viewers, this will enable the project to see precisely how many people have viewed each item, streamlining the monitoring process.

☰ SIENNA

SIENNA / Publications / Deliverable reports

Public deliverable reports

SIENNA methodology

Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead, Philip Brey, Zuzanna Warso, Tim Hanson, Lisa Tambornino, & Dirk Lanzerath. (2018). [SIENNA D1.1: The consortium's methodological handbook](#) (Version V0.6). Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4247384

State-of-the-art Reviews

Heidi Howard, Emilia Niemiec, & Alexandra Soulier. (2019). [SIENNA D2.1: State of the art review of human genomic technologies](#) (Version V0.4). Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4067912

Sean R. Jensen, Saskia Nagel, Philip Brey, Tanne Ditzel, Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead, & David Wright. (2018). [SIENNA D3.1: State-of-the-art Review: Human Enhancement](#) (Version V1.1). Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4066557

Figure 3. Example public deliverable reports page from the SIENNA project, using links to Zenodo

3 Communication strategy

3.1 Target audiences

In addition to the stakeholder groups identified in Section 2.3 of this deliverable, CVDLINK's communication strategy will target a broad, diverse audience, including the general public and the media, to raise awareness about the project's activities and objectives.

3.1.1 General public

The general public can be divided into the following sub-groups:

- Citizens who regularly consume news media but without a special interest in CVDs, medical research, or AI solutions;
- People with an interest in CVD research, medical innovation, and AI solutions, including professionals in the fields of medicine, computer science, technology development, information and communication technology (ICT), etc.;
- People with direct experience of CVDs, whether as patients themselves or through relationships with patients.

3.1.2 The media

The media will include the general and specialist press. The consortium will take a proactive approach to media engagement, directly reaching out to journalists with pitches proposing specific stories that can be taken from our work, offering to facilitate interviews with partners, and providing material such as public deliverables or other research findings.

To target the general press, we will compile a list of major publications which have historically covered topics related to CVDs, medical research, and AI development. We will identify specific journalists at these outlets and write tailored pitches which consider their previous work and editorial approaches when proposing coverage of our work.

To target the specialist press, which includes medical news outlets and trade publications, we will take a similar approach, compiling a list of outlets and a list of journalists at these outlets who may be interested in our work. Pitching stories to these specialist outlets exposes the project to audiences composed of professionals in related fields. This enables journalists to write with more technical detail and specificity, as writers for these outlets presume their readers have a higher degree of knowledge about the topics being covered.

3.1.3 Communication messages

For the public, the main messages will be general information about the project, such as objectives, anticipated outcomes, and information about the partners. The goal is to

generate awareness about the project, its potential impact on the mitigation and treatment of CVDs, and, by extension, its effect on the large sectors of society affected by CVDs, which are the leading cause of death in Europe and worldwide.

In addition to this general information, we will also communicate messages about the efficacy and trustworthiness of AI-powered medical tools. To achieve this, we will focus on communicating about topics including GDPR compliance, ethical approaches to privacy and data protection, and efforts to mitigate the potential harms of AI, such as transparency and explainability. We will present these topics in an engaging and accessible way, using visual and interactive elements including videos, infographics, and other means explained in Section 3.2, aiming to provide insight into the elements most likely to influence the public's trust in and acceptance of innovative AI tools.

Key messages may be adjusted throughout the project as outputs are published and external events arise. The timing of messaging is an important consideration and is outlined in Section 4.4.

3.2 Communication channels and tools

3.2.1 Project website

The project website was presented in Section 2.5.1 of this deliverable and is discussed in more detail in D1.5. As the most in-depth, publicly available resource about the project, the website will function as the epicentre of the communication and dissemination strategy, acting as a central repository for project information, updates, and more. It is considered the main communication channel that facilitates other communication activities, including blogs, social media, and media outreach.

3.2.2 Social media

Social media is a crucial way to reach the project's target audience and share spontaneous and casual updates alongside published research, blog articles, and other important information. The consortium agreed to establish a LinkedIn page. LinkedIn is a professional network commonly used by researchers, developers, NGOs, and other target audiences. The project will also have a YouTube page, which will enable awareness-raising among a more general audience.

LinkedIn also provides the option to create company pages, which are affiliated with a profile but operate as a separate board and can be a useful tool for organising and promoting cluster work. This option will be evaluated later in the project, once clustering activities begin.

TRI established the project's LinkedIn account in M06 (June 2024) and is responsible for managing it. The account is available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/cvdlink-project-900698314/>

Figure 4. CVDLINK LinkedIn page

Social media strategy

The topics addressed by CVDLINK, particularly AI and its applications in medicine, are currently widely discussed on LinkedIn, as well as in the media. The social media strategy aims to ensure that CVDLINK capitalises on this discussion, using it to extend the reach of the project’s communications. As such, we will expend significant effort in the early days of the project to connect with experts in AI, medicine, medical ethics, tech, and data security, as well as journalists. Alongside these efforts we will also connect with stakeholders across our key target audiences and other EC-funded projects. Although less time will be devoted to connecting with other pages once the project has a well-established base of connections, TRI will continue connecting with users on an ongoing basis throughout the project.

To ensure CVDLINK emerges as a voice within these conversations, we will post news and interesting content related to medical AI, data sharing, and other project themes. Project news, communication materials (such as factsheets and press releases), and website content will be shared, alongside public deliverables, publications, and conference highlights. We will aim to post twice weekly at varying times of day to reach as wide an audience as possible. Certain types of news, such as research breakthroughs, event updates, or press releases will be shared immediately, regardless of the time or day. The strategy is informed by the EC’s social media guide for EU funded Research and Innovation projects (Horizon Europe, 2023) and will be evaluated using social media analytics.

Social media posts will be used to direct traffic to the website. As much as possible, posts will include a link to the website (e.g., by concluding a post with the sentence “for more information, head to our website at <https://cvdlink-project.eu>”).

Contributions from all partners will support the growth of a strong base of connections, which in turn will enable CVDLINK to successfully deliver key messages to all stakeholder groups. Partners are asked to connect with the project on their institutions’ LinkedIn pages and, if they are active LinkedIn users, on their personal accounts. CVDLINK will share partners’ content when it is relevant to the project, and partners are asked to share

the project's content as much as possible in turn. Further, project partners are asked to help raise awareness about CVDLINK and its results by posting on their institutional or personal accounts and by providing content for social media posts to TRI.

Partners are encouraged to use images when posting on LinkedIn to encourage higher engagement. Only images that are taken at project events (with consent from participants), from CVDLINK materials (such as factsheets or flyers) or are free for reuse (under Creative Commons License) should be used.

3.2.3 Newsletters

Newsletters function as a tool for both communication (i.e., for sharing general information and updates about the project) and dissemination (i.e., for sharing project results), and as such are described in detail in the dissemination section of this document, under Section 2.5.2.

Particularly in the earlier stages of the project, before results are available, newsletters are a valuable communication tool to provide updates about the project, background information highlighting the project's significance (i.e., the scale of CVDs in society and the potential impacts of the project's results), and other material designed to give readers greater insight into the ideas and objectives underpinning the project. The newsletter will highlight results and project outputs as they become available.

3.2.4 Printed materials

SYNYO GmbH will lead the production of graphic design materials, including a pull-up banner, project factsheet, leaflet, and poster. These items are currently being developed and will form the basis of the project's "communication kit." An additional flyer may be made towards the end of the project to better present the results. They will be posted on the website and partners can present or distribute them at presentations or on social media.

Specialised materials tailored to specific events may be created upon partners' request. Any partners requesting such material should notify the WP8 lead with six weeks' notice.

Although these items are referred to as "printed materials," we will keep these digital-only as much as possible to avoid the production of waste, while recognising that in some instances (e.g., presentations at conferences) printed materials are necessary to generate impact.

3.2.5 Videos

SYNYO GmbH will also lead the production of two videos; one introducing the project, produced within the first year, and another version later in the project about specific results the consortium would like to promote. Towards the ends of the project, the consortium will evaluate whether further videos are an effective use of time, or if WP8 activities should focus more on events such as hackathons and workshops.

3.2.6 Infographics

SYNYO GmbH will produce a series of infographics to be shared on social media, and which all partners can use in presentations about the project. The first set of graphics will be issued in the first year and reflect the core themes underlying the project. These will be updated around the midway point of the project (M24) and again towards the end of the project to reflect major findings. If partners produce research findings that they would like represented in an infographic in between these periods, they should notify the WP8 lead.

3.2.7 Press releases

Press releases are an important way to keep the media informed about major findings and increase interest in CVDLINK and the topics it covers. Press releases will be prepared when newsworthy events occur, such as novel research findings or the delivery of presentations at high-impact events. Events are considered newsworthy if they are unique, haven't received media attention in the past, and have potentially significant impacts on society. As such, press releases will not cover standard or routine project milestones, except for the first press release announcing the project kick-off, which was created so partners could share material about the project while the website was under development. Ideally, press releases will be published semi-regularly (i.e., every 6 months). However, the decision to publish press releases will be determined by the production of newsworthy content, rather than an arbitrary timeline. As such, it is reasonable to anticipate that press releases will be concentrated towards the end of the project, when outputs are finalised.

In addition to being published on the website and shared on social media, TRI will send press releases directly to journalists as attachments on media pitches. This reflects the project's active approach to media engagement.

Partners will be asked to share press releases with their networks, through email, social media, and by sharing on their respective websites. Partners are asked to translate the press releases and forward them to local media and, if available, their respective institution's media offices. These activities will ensure the project receives media attention in a range of countries and languages.

3.2.8 Blogs/news items

Blogs and news items will be produced in collaboration with consortium partners and posted on the "news" section of the website. Blogs should provide insight into the project's activities, objectives, theoretical grounding, and results. Topics include:

- Blogs explaining the major findings from public deliverables
- Updates on project events, conferences, clustering workshops, etc.
- "Explainers", e.g., covering how certain technologies work or describing the theoretical approaches behind the project
- Summaries of publications, presentations, etc.

All partners are asked to contribute to the blog. TRI will facilitate their contributions by tracking what activities partners are involved in and scheduling bilateral conversations to discuss deadlines and partners' contributions.

Blogs play an important role, keeping the website updated with content that feeds into the newsletter and social media posting. To ensure this flow of content is regular, we aim to publish at least one blog per month.

The table below shows a preliminary timetable of partners' contributions to the blog. At the moment, these are largely based on public deliverables; more blog topics will be identified in collaboration with partners.

Blog topic	Date	Responsible partner(s)
Introducing the project: main objectives and anticipated outcomes	M07	TRI
Building trust in medical AI systems	M08	CERTH
Explainer: what data banks exist and why we'll use them	M09	TBD
Explainer: why use federated storage	M10	TBD
Insights from D2.1 CVDLINK user requirements, gaps, and challenges	M13	TAU
Insights from D2.2 CVDLINK full system design	M18	SIMAVI
Insights from D3.2 Interim versions of CVDLINK federated repository and data management tools	M31	KTU
Insights from D5.1 CVDLINK data joint ownership, sharing, use, and re-use framework	M32	TRI IE
Insights from D3.3 Final versions of CVDLINK federated repository and data management tools	M37	VER
Insights from D4.3 Final versions of CVDLINK pipelines for signal/image/-omics data	M42	VICOM
Insights from D5.2 The ethical handbook	M47	TRI
Insights from D6.4 Final CVDLINK integrated prototype and results of validation studies	M48	UMFCD
Others	TBD	TBD

Table 3. Preliminary blog schedule

4 Dissemination and communication management

This section clarifies partners' responsibilities with regards to dissemination and communication, outlines the consortium policies and procedures impacting dissemination and communication, and covers the timing of planned activities.

4.1 Visual identity

The visual identity is the project's unique brand and should be consistently presented across all communication and dissemination activities. The elements comprising the visual identity are the project logo, colour scheme, fonts, and templates.

Annex 9.1 outlines visual identity guidelines designed to ensure that CVDLINK is represented consistently across all communication and dissemination activities. All partners are asked to review these guidelines and adhere to them throughout the duration of the project.

For more details on the use of CVDLINK's visual identity, see Annex 9.1.

4.2 Responsibilities

As the WP8 lead, TRI will coordinate the communication and dissemination activities throughout the WP and leads T8.1 and T8.2, while SIMAVI leads T8.3 and SYNNO contributes to T8.1. However, as per the GA (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023) and this deliverable, all partners are considered responsible for the dissemination and communication of project results, through a range of activities including sharing on social media, publishing in scientific journals, and presentations at events.

Each partner is asked to designate a representative from their organisation responsible for their contributions to dissemination and communication and notify the DCM (TRI).

4.2.1 Funding acknowledgement

CVDLINK partners are contractually obligated to include the EU funding acknowledgement on all CVDLINK materials, both on- and off-line.

As per Article 17.2 of the GA (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023), all materials must include a variation of the official EU funding logo, pictured below. These can be downloaded from the EC's download centre for visual elements https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en (European Commission, n.d.).

Figure 5. Funding emblem in horizontal alignment

Figure 6. Funding emblem in vertical alignment

Article 17.3 of the GA (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023) stipulates that all dissemination and communication material must also include the following disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4.3 Policies and procedures

WP leaders are responsible for:

- Identifying results suitable for dissemination and communication and sharing these with the DCM
- Choosing the most appropriate partner to lead the dissemination of the result (this will usually be the partner generating the result)
- Helping the responsible partner identify the potential audience, with the support of the WP8 lead
- When considering submitting an article to a journal, leads should help the responsible partner identify the most appropriate journal, in collaboration with the WP8 lead

Further, all partners must keep in mind the following:

- All dissemination and communication materials must comply with both the project branding guidelines (see Section 4.1 and Annex 9.1) and the funding acknowledgement (see Section 4.2.1 and Articles 17.2 and 17.3 of the GA)
- The project coordinator and WP8 lead will provide support to ensure compliance with project branding

- All deliverables and presentations must be prepared using the provided Word document and PowerPoint templates
- All partners should obtain consortium approval of dissemination materials before distribution
- All partners must give notice of any planned publication at least 30 calendar days before the publication

4.4 Timing

The table below offers a preliminary timeline of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, broken down into specific tasks.

Activity	Task	Partners	Dates
Communication activities	Website (design, management, updates) and	TRI, ALL	M01-M48 Website, M06
	Social media (LinkedIn)	TRI, ALL	M06-M48
	Templates (deliverables, presentations)	TRI, SIMAVI	Delivered M03
	Promotional package (leaflets, posters, infographics, video)	SYNYO, TRI	M06-M48
	Writing press releases and blogs	TRI, ALL	M02-M48
	Newsletter writing and distribution	TRI	M07, M13, M19, M25, M31, M37, M43, M48
Dissemination/communication processes	Media contacts search	TRI, ALL	M07-M48
	Stakeholders contact list	ALL	M03-M48
Dissemination activities	Attending conferences	ALL	M01-M48
	Clustering workshops	ALL	M13-M48
	Publishing journal articles	ALL	M07-M48
Monitoring activities	Monitoring project outcomes and dissemination activities	TRI, ALL	M01-M48

Table 4. Preliminary timeline of dissemination and communication activities

5 Potential barriers that may hinder dissemination

The table below outlines potential barriers hindering the efficacy of the dissemination and communication strategy, including an assessment of risk and mitigation measures.

Risk	Risk level (low, medium, high)	Mitigation measure
Stakeholders disinterested in the project and its outputs	Low/medium	The DCM will monitor the engagement of stakeholders across different target audiences, which will enable the early identification of any target audiences who are not engaging with the project. The DCM will use this information to focus on tailoring messages to attract the interest of these groups, as well as facilitating participation at events, publications, and other channels targeting these end users.
Stakeholders unaware of project results	Low	This risk will be countered by a robust presence online, at key events, and in high-impact publications. These will be selected by considering which venues are the most appropriate to reach the target group(s) that will benefit the most from a specific output, to ensure project results are adequately disseminated to stakeholders.
Low stakeholder attendance at workshops, trainings, and project events	High	To counter this risk, the strategy ensures that events are promoted through high-impact channels and directed at the appropriate target audiences. Further, all partners should draw on their respective networks to promote the event. Events will be made hybrid or have a live-streaming option to encourage participation from people who are unable to travel.
Low number of subscribers to the newsletter	Low/medium	This strategy establishes a collaborative, GDPR-compliant approach to building a contact list with contacts from all partners' networks on the basis of legitimate interest. Furthermore, the newsletter subscription box is prominently displayed on the website and will be regularly promoted on the project's social media.

Table 5. List of risks and mitigation measures

6 Evaluation and monitoring

To evaluate the impact of the dissemination and communication strategy, all activities will be monitored and evaluated for efficacy. As this deliverable is a living document scheduled to be updated at the project’s midway point (M24) and before the project’s end date (M48), this strategy will be evaluated and amended, if necessary, throughout the project. In between these updates, all partners are asked to keep a record of any dissemination and communication activities in which they partake, as well as the target audience reached, to ensure we are on track to meet the project KPIs.

To monitor these activities, we will use a dissemination and communication monitoring spreadsheet, in which partners will record details of any actions they have performed, as well as the audiences they have reached (Annex 9.6). We will use the spreadsheet alone to monitor dissemination and communication activities as they often overlap, and to streamline the process and reduce the need to collate information from multiple sources. The spreadsheet is designed to reflect the categories of information the European Commission requests for project dissemination, mimicking the types of information requested at the project reviews. Guidelines for filling in the spreadsheet are included in the document, and the DCM will regularly remind partners at meetings and over email to fill it in.

Any feedback from target audiences gathered at workshops, networking events, or other means should be recorded in a shared space. Further, any new contacts established by partners should be recorded in the project’s contact list, which is securely saved on the CVDLINK SharePoint.

6.1 Dissemination and communication KPIs

The table below illustrates a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the channels used in dissemination and communication. KPIs will be monitored using the monitoring spreadsheet (see Section 6 and Annex 9.6), at project meetings, and at the interim and final reviews.

Instruments	Expected number of participants/beneficiaries	Target audience
Newsletters	>200 subscribers; newsletters	8 All stakeholders, including the public and the media
Project website	20,000-30,000 unique visitors = excellent 10,000 – 20,000 = good 5,000 – 10,000 = fair	All stakeholders, including the public and the media

Social media (LinkedIn)	>2,000 connections = excellent 1,000 – 2,000 connections = good 500 – 1,000 connections = fair	All stakeholders, including the public and the media
Social media impressions	>15,000	All stakeholders, including the public and the media
Press releases	At least 3 throughout the duration of the project	Media, public
Videos	At least 2	All stakeholders, including the public and the media
Flyers/brochures/other promotional material	>300 downloaded and distributed at events	All stakeholders, including the public and the media
Peer-reviewed scientific journal publications	>20 = excellent >10 = good >5 = fair	Academia, industry
Presentations at third-party workshops and conferences	>10	Academia, industry
Synergies with initiatives and networks	>10 initiatives and networks	Academia, industry
Participation in CVDLINK workshops, hackathons, and clustering activities	Active participation of at least 100 people overall	Academic and industry experts involved in co-creation workshops
		Tech developers
		Academics, industry in other projects and initiatives

Table 6. Dissemination and communication KPIs

7 Conclusion

The dissemination and communication strategy defined in this deliverable lays out the required tools, channels, and best practices to promote the project and its results. The deliverable explains the strategic importance of disseminating a coherent message aligned with the scope of the CVDLINK project.

Furthermore, the document outlines guidelines partners should adopt when communicating project results and outputs. These include obligations, such as acknowledging EU funding, and considerations such as tailoring messaging for channels with different audiences. The document identifies target audiences and potential events, publication opportunities, and initiatives to collaborate with.

The document addresses potential risks and proposes measures to mitigate these risks, and outlines internal policies related to monitoring and evaluating the efficacy of the proposed strategy.

The communication and dissemination activities will be updated at the end of each reporting period with a formal update required in M24, and the strategy will be adjusted if necessary. Further, a deliverable with all engagement activities will be submitted at the end of the project. Partners' dissemination and communication activities will be monitored on an ongoing basis to ensure the consortium reaches the anticipated KPIs.

This report will serve as a guide for the upcoming activities under T8.1, T8.2, and T8.3, and reports that fall under WP8.

8 References

CVDLINK Consortium, 2023. *Grant Agreement*, s.l.: s.n.

European Commission, n.d. *Download centre for visual elements*. [Online]
Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

GDPR, 2016. *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council*, s.l.: European Parliament and of the Council.

Horizon Europe, 2023. *HE Social Media Guide: Using social media in EU funded R&I projects*. [Online]

Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/social-media-guide_he_en.pdf

Horizon Europe, 2023. *HE Social Media Guide: Using social media in EU-funded R&I projects*. [Online]

Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/social-media-guide_he_en.pdf

9 Annexes

9.1 Visual identity guidelines

TRI created a visual identity guide, which is intended to ensure the project's unique brand is communicated consistently across all dissemination and communication activities, including publications, presentations, and marketing material. The present section outlines guidance on using the logo, fonts, colours, and templates correctly.

All partners should follow these guidelines in all the project's dissemination and communication activities and adhere to the funding acknowledgement requirements outlined in Section 4.2.1.

Logo

The logo may be used in a few variations. The first is a complete, horizontally oriented logo, with the heart symbol and the project name (see Figure 5).

Figure 7. Horizontal logo

The second alternative is a vertically oriented version of the same (Figure 6).

Figure 8. Vertical logo

Partners may also use the heart symbol alone (Figure 7).

Figure 9. Image-only logo

In any of these forms, the logo should be presented in the project colours. However, if a dark background is used, white versions of the three logos may be used.

When using the logo, partners must ensure the correct proportions are maintained when the logo's size is adjusted. Partners should also ensure the logo isn't too small to be readable. Partners must always use the official logo, available in the project's SharePoint, rather than recreating it. If partners are recreating any elements from the logo, they should use the original high-resolution images or vector files and avoid working from screenshots.

Colour scheme

The project's main colours are composed of shades of green and white, with a subsidiary colour palette with a wider range of options. In order to maintain a coherent visual identity, no other colours should be used. The HEX and RGB codes are listed below.

CVDLINK colour scheme: main colours			
Colour 1:	Colour 2:	Colour 3:	Colour 4:
HEX: 32 4f 3f	HEX: 54 6f 60	HEX: e1 e3 82	HEX: f2 f2 e8
RGB: 50 80 63	RGB: 85 112 97	RGB: 225 229 131	RGB: 244 245 235

Table 7. Main colours

CVDLINK colour scheme: subsidiary colours			
Colour 1:	Colour 2:	Colour 3:	Colour 4:
HEX: ec a9 3a	HEX: 54 6f 60	HEX: 32 4f 3f	HEX: 69 8e 79
RGB: 238 170 58	RGB: 85 112 97	RGB: 50 80 63	RGB: 105 143 123
Colour 5:	Colour 6:	Colour 7:	
HEX: 89 b7 9d	HEX: 8d d1 c8	HEX: d7 51 64	
RGB: 138 184 158	RGB: 141 210 201	RGB: 216 81 100	

Table 8. Subsidiary colours

Fonts

The following fonts have been selected to use throughout the project.

- Open Sans for text in PowerPoints, deliverables, and other Word documents
- Helvetica for the website

Templates

PowerPoint templates

To avoid inconsistency across presentations, SIMAVI created a PowerPoint for partners to use in internal and external presentations. An initial version of the PowerPoint was created for the kick-off meeting in M2 and revised to reflect the updated visual identity in M3.

Partners must use the template created by SIMAVI, taking care to ensure the funding logo and statement are untouched. The Slide Master contains the correct logos for headings and body text, which will appear automatically.

Figure 10. Example slide from PowerPoint template

Word template

TRI and SIMAVI created a deliverable template, which is available in the project's SharePoint. Partners should use this template for all deliverables without modifying the predefined fonts and colours for texts and headers.

A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis, and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions

DX.X [Title of Deliverable]

Figure 11. Title page of deliverable template

9.2 Stakeholder organisations

The table below lists some stakeholder organisations the project may target through dissemination activities. The list is not exhaustive and will be updated throughout the duration of the project. Organisations marked with an asterisk (*) have pre-existing connections with CVDLINK partners, which will be leveraged throughout the project.

Organisation Name	Category	Country
EIT-Health*	Research and development network	Germany
GAIA-X: A Federated Secure Data Infrastructure*	Research and development network	Belgium
Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation*	Research and development network	Belgium

European Association of Research and Technology*	Research and development network	Belgium
Big Data Value Association – Data, AI, and Robotics*	Research and development network	Belgium
European Society of Cardiology*	Professional organisation	Belgium
European Society for Person-Centred Healthcare (ESPCH)*	Professional organisation	UK and Spain
European Society for AI in Medicine*	Professional organisation	Italy
International Agency for Research on Cancer (WHO)*	NGO	France
Irish Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Ireland
Global Heart Hub	Patient organisation, NGO	Global
British Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	UK
European Heart Network	Patient organisation, NGO	Belgium
Belgian Heart League	Patient organisation, NGO	Belgium
Foundation of Health and Heart	Patient organisation, NGO	Bosnia & Herzegovina
Croatian Heart House Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Croatia
Danish Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Denmark
Faroese Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Denmark

Finnish Heart Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Finland
German Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Germany
Hellenic Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Greece
Heart Foundation of the Hungarian Society of Cardiology	Patient organisation, NGO	Hungary
Icelandic Heart Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Iceland
Israeli Heart Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Israel
Italian Society for Cardiovascular Prevention	Patient organisation, NGO	Italy
Italian Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Italy
Lithuanian Heart Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Lithuania
Northern Ireland Chest Heart & Stroke	Patient organisation, NGO	UK
Portuguese Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Portugal
Romanian Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Romania
Serbian Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Serbia
Slovenian Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Slovenia
Spanish Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Spain

Swedish Heart and Lung Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Sweden
Swedish Heart Lung Association	Patient organisation, NGO	Sweden
Swiss Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Switzerland
Dutch Heart Foundation	Patient organisation, NGO	Netherlands
The Dutch Association for People with Cardiovascular Diseases	Patient organisation, NGO	Netherlands
EHTEL: the European eHealth Stakeholder Platform	Research and development network	Belgium
European Public Health Alliance	Professional association	Belgium
European Health Data Space Initiatives*	Research and development network	EU-wide
European Health Task Force	Policy making	Belgium
Health Hub	Digital innovation	Greece
1+MG	Research and development network / Open Science platform	EU-wide
Beyond 1 Million Genomes	EU-funded project	UK
European Open Science Cloud	Open Science platform	EU-wide
NFP4Health	EU-funded project	EU-wide

COCIR	Professional association	Belgium
MedTech Europe	Professional association	Belgium
DIGITALEUROPE	Professional association	Belgium
Healthtech Ireland	Professional association	Ireland
AdvaMed	Professional association	US
British Healthcare Trades Association	Professional association	UK
EATRIS (European Infrastructure for Translational medicine)	Technology developers	Netherlands
Digital Health Europe	EU-funded projects	Germany
Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society (HIMSS)	Professional association	US
Irish Cardiac Society	Professional association	Ireland
British Cardiovascular Society	Professional association	UK
Artificial Intelligence, Innovation & Society (AIIS)	EU-funded project	Spain
The Health Research Board	Research and development network	Ireland
EuropaBio	Professional association	Belgium
European Health Management Association	Professional association	Belgium

Health Research Charities Ireland	Research and development network	Ireland
H2020 Incisive*	EU-funded project	Italy
H2020 ProCare4Life	EU-funded project	Portugal
H2020 MED-CoBraD	EU-funded project	Greece
PerCard Project*	EU-funded project	Finland
H2020 FeatureCloud*	EU-funded project	Germany
H2020 AEGLE*	EU-funded project	Greece
Digital EUCAIM*	EU-funded project	Netherlands
H2020 HOSMARTAI	EU-funded project	Belgium
Research Data Alliance	Research and development network	Europe, USA, Australia

Table 9. CVDLINK stakeholder organisations

9.3 Preliminary list of journals

Journal name	Details	Impact factor*	Link
BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making	Publications cover the design, development, use, and evaluation of medical information and decision-making technologies.	3.298	https://bmcmmedinformdecismak.biomedcentral.com/
Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine	Covers computing methodology and software systems related to all aspects of biomedical	6.1	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computer-methods-and-

	research and medical practice.		programs-in-biomedicine
Artificial Intelligence in Medicine	Interdisciplinary journal publishing articles related to the theory and practice of AI in medicine, medically-oriented human biology, and health care.	7.5	https://sciencedirect.com/journal/artificial-intelligence-in-medicine
IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics	Focused on advances in biomedical and health informatics at the intersections of health, healthcare, life science, and biomedicine.	7.7	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=6221020
Nature Scientific Reports	Open-access journal publishing peer-reviewed research from the natural science, medicine, psychology, and engineering.	4.6	https://www.nature.com/srep/
European Heart Journal	Publishes clinical and scientific research on all aspects of cardiovascular medicine.	39.3	https://academic.oup.com/eurheartj
Journal of Responsible Technology	Takes a broad view on responsible technology and publishes research on this topic across domains, with a particular interest in research with recognisable practical applications.	3.77	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-responsible-technology
European Journal of Public Health	Interdisciplinary research related to public health and policy with a focus on Europe, although contributions to global	4.4	https://academic.oup.com/eurpub

	health issues are welcome when relevant		
Journal of Biomedical Informatics	Focused on the methodology related to biomedical informatics. Publications should develop a novel approach to address a real-world biomedical or clinical issue and evaluate its efficacy in relation to current state of the art.	4.5	https://sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-biomedical-informatics
CSBJ: The Smart Hospital Section	Focus on emerging technologies transforming health and care systems, with a special interest in the integration of AI systems in health and care facilities.	9.1	https://www.csbj.org/SmartHospital
Medical Image Analysis	Publishes new research about medical and biological image analysis, with a focus on research on the applications of computer vision, virtual reality, and robotics to biomedical imaging.	10.9	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/medical-image-analysis
Springer: AI and Society	Focused on understanding the potential impacts of pervasive technology for societies; submissions should address the societal dimension of research.	3	https://link.springer.com/journal/146
Journal of Global Health	General medical journal focused on global health	7.6	https://jogh.org/

Ethics, Medicine, and Public Health	Covers all ethical aspects of science, biomedical research, and public health.	1.6	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/ethics-medicine-and-public-health
Ethics and Information Technology	Broadly focused on the ethical, social, and political dilemmas/challenges/effects of the adoption, use, and development of ICT	3.6	https://link.springer.com/journal/10676

Table 10. Preliminary list of journals

*Impact factors taken from journal websites as of 01 June 2024.

9.4 Preliminary list of events

Event name	Audience	Website
GAIA-X Health Data Space Event	Data scientists, researchers, tech developers	https://gaia-x.eu/events/
EIT Health Summit	Healthcare innovators, researchers	https://summit.eithealth.eu/
HEALTHINF	ICT professionals, researchers, medical informatics professionals	https://healthinf.scitevents.org/
Computing Cardiology in	Scientists, professionals from the fields of medicine, physics, engineering, and computer science	https://cinc.org/
AI+Data	Health professionals, data scientists, researchers, tech developers	https://digitalhealthaidata.com/

European Public Health Conference	Researchers, policymakers, professionals	academics, healthcare	https://ephconference.eu/
MICCAI – medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Interventions	Medical professionals, healthcare professionals	informatics researchers,	https://miccai.org/
AIME – International Conference of AI in Medicine	Researchers, academics, data scientists		https://aime24.aimedicine.info/
Intelligent Health Summit	Researchers, academics	data scientists,	https://intelligenthealth.ai/
ISPHPM – Public Health and Preventive Medicine	Healthcare professionals, researchers, academics		https://www.spectrumconferences.com/2024/isphpm

Table 11. Preliminary list of events

9.5 CVDLINK press release – February 2024

AI to Revolutionize Cardiovascular Care

The CVDLINK project kicks off in Bucharest, Romania

For immediate release

Date: 22/02/2024

CVDLINK, a new EU-funded project bringing together an international team of clinicians, researchers, and ethicists to explore data-driven approaches to cardiovascular care, kicked off in Bucharest last month. The project is focusing on harnessing Artificial Intelligence (AI) to reduce the healthcare burden and human cost of cardiovascular diseases (CVD).

CVDs are the leading cause of death globally, taking an estimated 17.9 million lives each year. Hospitals and regional health authorities collect data about CVD patients which, if analysed, could provide researchers with insights into the characteristics, predictors, and outcomes of CVD cases across regions. However, data sharing is hampered by unclear ethical and legal frameworks, and heterogenous, siloed data. CVDLINK aims to integrate

and analyse these disparate sources and facilitate data sharing to create medical AI tools for the effective prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of CVDs.

“It is clear that we need evidence-based approaches to the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular disease,” said Monica Florea, coordinator of CVDLINK. “Our project will contribute to this goal by linking data sources to create AI-driven tools designed to meet the needs of healthcare professionals while centring ethical and legal principles such as privacy, explainability, and bias mitigation.”

CVDLINK includes clinicians, AI developers, medical researchers, and ethicists from across Europe and beyond. The project partners are: [Software Imagination & Vision](#), [VicomTech](#), [Tampere University](#), [Aristotle University of Thessaloniki](#), [Tampere University Hospital](#), [Trilateral Research](#), [Technical University Darmstadt](#), [Veracell](#), [Athens Medical Group](#), [CERTH](#), [Universität Hamburg](#), [Carol Davila University of Medicine and Pharmacy](#), [Hillel Yaffe Medical Center](#), [Kineret – the Israel Health Data-Lake at the Ministry of Health](#), [Institute of Cardiology at Moldova's Institute of Public Health](#), [Wellics](#), [Kaunas University of Technology](#), [University of Tartu](#), and [SYNYO GmbH](#).

For press queries, please contact: cvdlink@simavi.ro

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9.6 CVDLINK monitoring spreadsheet

Below are screenshots of the spreadsheet used to record dissemination and communication activities, which ask for the categories of information required for reporting. All partners are asked to record their activities on the spreadsheet on an ongoing basis.

for stakeholder engagement and dissemination of information

8 Feb. 24

This document, prepared by Trilateral Research Ltd, provides the justification for the processing of personal data in the CVDLINK project and, specifically, the compilation of a contact list of stakeholders whom we will contact periodically by means of an e-mail or press release or newsletter or other means.

The CVDLINK contact list contains the names, titles, organisations and e-mail addresses of stakeholders whom we believe might be interested in the results of our project as well as stakeholders who have asked to be added to our contact list.

Data processing in the CVDLINK project includes collecting contact details as well as sending information to contacts. Most lawful bases require that processing is 'necessary' for a specific purpose. In the instance of our project, the collection of contact data and sending contacts information about our project results are necessary for the project to achieve impact by supporting research ethics committees and other research bodies with training to anticipate and mitigate ethical issues in new technologies. Hence, our project results have a larger social purpose than simply benefiting the consortium partners ("the beneficiaries" in the EC's terminology).

For EU-funded projects, such as ours, two legal documents are particularly relevant.

The first is the Grant Agreement (GA), Article 17.1 of which states that beneficiaries of Horizon Europe projects have an obligation to promote the project and its results: "Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner."

Article 17.1 clearly indicates that consortia are obliged to disseminate their results to multiple audiences, which implies the need to compile a contact list targeted at multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner, i.e., not just a random list of people who visit the project's website and ask to be put on the contact list. It has to be a *targeted* and *strategic* contact list. Hence, we consider that the GA serves as a valuable justification for the CVDLINK consortium to process personal data for this purpose.

The second is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Article 6 of which provides for several possible legal bases for the processing of personal data. For example, Article 6(1)(a) allows the processing of personal data with the **consent** of the individual (the data subject). The GDPR sets a high standard for consent to be considered valid and it can always be withdrawn.

Another basis is Article 6(1)(f) which allows processing necessary for the **legitimate interests** pursued by the controller or by a third party. Our project has a legitimate interest for processing personal data, which stems from GA Article 17.1, as referenced above. We are obliged to inform stakeholders, including the public, about our project, disseminate and communicate its results.

Legitimate interest is the most flexible lawful basis for processing, but must be carefully assessed in each specific case. The existence of a legitimate interest also depends on the **reasonable expectations** of the persons concerned, where we use people's data in ways they would reasonably expect and where such use would have a minimal privacy impact, and where there is a compelling justification for the processing. Most stakeholders on our contact list have their e-mail addresses on their organisation's website, that is, they have already made their contact details public, hence, they must have a reasonable expectation that others will contact them. Others have asked to be on the contact list.

In addition, a balancing exercise must be conducted between the legitimate interests of the project and the interests of the data subjects concerned. For this balancing, CVDLINK consulted the website of the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), the UK data protection authority, which offers detailed guidance on how to conduct the balancing exercise¹ and on which the following is adapted.

The ICO says that there are three elements to the legitimate interest basis. We must

- *identify a legitimate interest* – As stated above, we have a legitimate interest, under Article 17.1, to process personal contact details, as mentioned above, in order to create impact for our EU-funded project.
- *show that the processing is necessary to achieve it* – 'Necessary' means that the processing must be a targeted and proportionate way of achieving our purpose. We must collect the contact details for engineers, local authorities, public authorities, civil society organisations and community leaders across the EU in order to inform them about how our project results could help them measure and prioritise investments in energy efficiency. The processing is necessary as we could not reasonably achieve the same result in another way.
- *balance it against the individual's interests, rights and freedoms* – see below, where we have done a balancing test, and are confident that the consortium's legitimate interests do not override the individual's interests or fundamental rights.

As noted below, our processing of personal data will not cause harm any more than any other e-mail to our stakeholders. We are not using people's data in ways they would find intrusive or which could cause them harm. We will always offer stakeholders an option to unsubscribe from our contact list.

Safeguards

Even though we believe there are no significant risks to the data subjects of their being on our contact list and sending them relevant news, we have considered safeguards to reduce further any risks, as follows: Trilateral Research Ltd commits to keep its contact list in a secure, password-protected file to which only a limited number of individuals will have access on a need-to-know basis.

As we wish to rely on legitimate interests as the basis for processing data on our contact list, we have conducted this legitimate interest assessment (LIA) before we start the

processing. According to the ICO, an LIA is a type of light-touch risk assessment based on the specific context and circumstances. It helps ensure that processing is lawful. Recording our LIA also helps to demonstrate compliance in line with our accountability obligations under GDPR Articles 5(2) and 24.

The ICO posits the following questions as part of its LIA exercise. Opposite each question in the left-hand column, we give our response in the right-hand column.

First, identify the legitimate interest(s).

Why do you want to process the data – what are you trying to achieve?	We wish to inform stakeholders about the development in the CVDLINK project of novel, data-driven tools that will help them diagnose, treat, and manage cardiovascular diseases
Who benefits from the processing? In what way?	The consortium partners benefit from the processing because they are able to inform our contacts about the results of our project. Stakeholders also benefit because they will remain informed about technological and clinical advancements in their field.
Are there any wider public benefits to the processing?	Yes, enhanced secondary effects from mitigating and better addressing cardiovascular disease from the use of the CVDLINK results and tools will improve health and quality-of-life outcomes.
How important are those benefits?	Essential to improving public health and boosting public trust in AI-driven medical technologies. Ensures that advancements in technology is melded with regulatory compliance and ethical and privacy concerns.
What would the impact be if you couldn't go ahead?	It would affect our ability to fulfil our contractual obligation.

<p>Would your use of the data be unethical or unlawful in any way?</p>	<p>No, we will follow good data protection practices and follow established ethical guidelines.</p>
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Second, apply the necessity test.

<p>Does this processing actually help to further that interest?</p>	<p>Yes, this processing will help our legitimate interest to inform Stakeholders about the development of tools aimed at helping them.</p>
<p>Is it a reasonable way to go about it?</p>	<p>Yes, it is the only way to enter into direct contact with the Stakeholder – apart from telephoning them directly, which would be more intrusive than an e-mail.</p>
<p>Is there another less intrusive way to achieve the same result?</p>	<p>No, see above. Calling would be more intrusive. However, this activity is being supplemented by other less intrusive, although less effective means, such as networking at relevant events. However, this method would not allow the project to reach a critical mass of relevant individuals who could benefit from the information we are sharing.</p>

Third, apply the balancing test.

By applying the balancing test (based on the questions below), we consider the impact of our processing and whether it overrides the interest we have identified.

<p>What is the nature of your relationship with the individual?</p>	<p>The individuals in this case are the Stakeholders across the EU. Stakeholders are our targets for the tools being developed in our project and so this relationship is significant.</p>
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<p>Is any of the data particularly sensitive or private?</p>	<p>No. We are collecting only basic contact data that is already publicly available. In addition to the contact details we have compiled, some stakeholders visiting the CVDLINK website have asked to be put on our contact list. We keep a log of such requests.</p>
<p>Would people expect you to use their data in this way?</p>	<p>Yes, especially Stakeholders, who have put their contact details on their websites. Hence, they must expect that people will contact them.</p> <p>In addition, the circulation of e-mails informing stakeholders about EU-funded project outcomes is a widespread practice in the field, and we assume that the carefully-selected stakeholders will receive this communication positively.</p>
<p>Are you happy to explain it to them?</p>	<p>Yes. We will inform our contacts about the mission of our project and how its results could be of assistance to them. We will also inform them about the project's privacy policy.</p>
<p>Are some people likely to object or find it intrusive?</p>	<p>No, as mentioned above, they have an interest in knowing about the project's results.</p>
<p>What is the possible impact on the individual?</p>	<p>There is no negative impact on the individual. We expect only a positive impact, in the sense that Stakeholders will become aware of how our project's results could help them. Typically, we would expect to e-mail our Stakeholder contacts no more than a few times a year.</p>
<p>How big an impact might it have on them?</p>	<p>As above.</p>

<p>Are you processing children’s data?</p>	<p>No. We do not aim to do this.</p>
<p>Are any of the individuals vulnerable in any other way?</p>	<p>Not that we are aware of.</p>
<p>Can you adopt any safeguards to minimise the impact?</p>	<p>We want to maximise the (positive) impact of or project. However, as noted above, we are implementing safeguards to protect our contact list – notably, our contact list file is securely stored, password-protected, and only a few individuals have access to the file. For further details, see the project’s privacy policy.</p>
<p>Can you offer an opt-out?</p>	<p>Yes, we include an “unsubscribe” option for all our communications with stakeholders such as newsletters, press releases and project flyers.</p>

The decision on legitimate interest

Based on the foregoing, we conclude that legitimate interest, Article 6 (1)(f), is an appropriate basis for our processing personal data, as described above. We are confident that our legitimate interests are not overridden by any risks to the data subject.

Next steps

We will inform our contacts that we are relying on legitimate interest for the processing of their contact details, and we will explain what this interest is, especially to draw to the attention of Stakeholders how the CVDLINK project findings will help them improve capacity in the research ethics approval process and identify ethical issues in new technology.

We understand that if we want to process the personal data for a new purpose, we may be able to continue processing under the legitimate interest provision as long as our new purpose is compatible with our original purpose. If necessary or useful, we will conduct a new LIA to demonstrate compliance with the legislation.

We will keep this record of our legitimate interest assessment (LIA) on file in order to demonstrate compliance with legislation, if required. We will keep our LIA under review, and repeat it if circumstances change.

9.8 Individual partners' dissemination and communication plans

Partners were asked to submit brief descriptions of their institutions' planned dissemination and communication activities. These are indicative plans and will likely change throughout the duration of the project.

9.8.1 SIMAVI

SIMAVI intends to share the results of the project with the Romanian ICT industry via national events and to present the project results to eHealth stakeholders by attending relevant events and conferences.

Also, SIMAVI will use the organisation's social media channels to promote and communicate about the CVDLINK project to increase project visibility and will contribute to the dissemination and communication strategies.

Moreover, SIMAVI will organize clustering events to increase visibility for the CVDLINK results, share knowledge and expertise, and foster synergies. The projects funded in the same call (HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05) will be approached for possible collaborations. The scope of the events (workshops) would be to reach policy makers and to leverage on the potential of the application of data sharing strategies and data-driven tools in cardiology.

9.8.2 VICOM

VICOM will disseminate CVDLINK activities and achievements to national and international industrial partners, academy and clinical collaborators, and local authorities. It is planned to present CVDLINK at several health-technology related events in which VICOM participates. VICOM will lead the dissemination of project-related results on medical image analysis pipelines by publishing at annual conferences such as Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Interventions (MICCAI), the largest international medical imaging conference, International Symposium of Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), or the International Conference on Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery (CARS). Preliminary results will be extended for submission to high-impact journals in the field, such as Medical Image Analysis or Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine. Additionally, together with other partners, VICOM will disseminate the work on signal and genomic data analysis in relevant international conferences.

VICOM has dedicated departments for Technology Transfer, International Projects, and Marketing and Communications, which will assist the project implementation team in reaching dissemination channels, including industry, academy, and national newspapers

and television such as www.elcorreo.com and www.eitb.eus. VICOM will also add a short description of the project to their website.

9.8.3 TAU

The primary dissemination activities planned by TAU are:

- Internal dissemination: TAU will present their work within CVDLINK, and the project more broadly, at local events including the Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology's annual research day event, events at the Finnish Cardiovascular Research Centre, and Tampere's Seminars.
- Scientific conferences: project results will be presented in relevant scientific conferences in the area of biomedical engineering, such as Computing in Cardiology.
- Scientific publications: Publications are planned on topics related to WP2 (Current use of risk assessment tools) and WP4 (data processing pipelines). Presentations in biomedical engineering conferences will also include articles in conference proceedings.
- Other events: TAU will build awareness of CVDLINK by participating in other events. For example, TAU's Antti Vehkaoja will present the CVDLINK project at the final consortium meeting of PARQ cost action in May 2024 to the project consortium and other participants (the project focuses on facilitating research on sudden cardiac arrest, see their website at <https://parq-cost.eu/>).

9.8.4 AUTH

AUTH, an academic institution with expertise in cardiovascular research, will leverage its dual role as a data provider and AI developer in its dissemination plan. Over the next four years, we will strategically showcase our research advancements and findings in both medical science and AI development.

In particular, we aim to disseminate our work through various channels, including both medical and technical-oriented academic conferences, such as:

- 47th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), Copenhagen, Denmark (<https://embc.embs.org/2025>)
- 35th Medical Informatics Europe Conference (#MIE2025) – Glasgow, Scotland (<https://mie2025.efmi.org/>)
- 13th International conference on Bio-inspired systems and signal processing, Porto, Portugal (<https://biosignals.scitevents.org/>)
- Belgrade Bioinformatics Conference, Annual Bioinformatics conference in Belgrade
- The IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering, Annual Conference
- Computing in Cardiology, annual conference

- The work on Deep Learning with omics data will be presented in DYNALIFE project WG1-WG2 Interaction Meeting - Data driven evidence: theoretical models and complex biological data, June 5 - 7, 2024, Thessaloniki
- ESC Congress 2025, 29 August to 1 September, Madrid, Spain

Additionally, we plan to publish our findings in high-impact peer reviewed journals such as:

- Scientific reports
- Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine
- Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine
- Computers in Biology and Medicine
- BMC Bioinformatics
- JACC: Heart Failure
- European Journal of Heart Failure

Furthermore, we will leverage digital platforms such as webinars and social media to engage with a wider audience, including clinicians, researchers, policymakers, and the general public, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration. Finally, the approaches that will be adopted in CVDLINK will be presented in post and undergraduate in the school of medicine of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, as well as the annual medical conferences at the AUTH and national level. Through these concerted efforts, we aim to maximize the impact of our research and contribute to the advancement of both medical science and artificial intelligence technologies.

9.8.5 TAUH

TAUH will focus on disseminating results via publications at high quality international scientific journals and presentations at suitable international conferences, such as those organized by the European Atherosclerosis Society (EAS).

9.8.6 TRI

As the WP8 lead, TRI will be involved in all dissemination and communication activities. TRI will focus on publicizing project updates and findings to professional and general audiences, as well as policymakers. We will make public deliverables available on the website, pitch stories about the project findings to trade and general publications, track journals and conferences partners may wish to participate in, and manage the website and social media. TRI will monitor journals, conferences, and workshops on an ongoing basis to flag potential publication and presentation opportunities to partners. In addition, TRI will promote relevant results through our monthly “Trilateral Insights” blog, in line with TRI’s corporate marketing strategy.

9.8.7 TUDa

The following communication and dissemination activities are planned by TUDa within CVDLINK:

Scientific Publications: we aim to publish research findings, methodologies, and outcomes in reputable scientific journals related to cardiovascular disease, machine learning, and signal processing. Potential journals are, for example, PLOS Digital Health, Scientific Reports, Physiological Measurement, BioMedical Engineering OnLine, Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing, IEEE JBHI.

Scientific Conferences: To amplify the project's impact, we will attend prestigious conferences such as the Computing in Cardiology or the IEEE EMBC. In addition to presentations, we will engage in workshops and panel discussions, which will facilitate networking with experts and stakeholders, fostering collaborations and enhancing visibility.

Social Media and Press Releases: Utilizing social media channels and our own website, as well as issuing press releases to disseminate project updates, achievements, and relevant news to a wider audience.

9.8.8 VERACELL

Veracell will disseminate knowledge and information about the CVDLINK project, aimed at raising awareness and promoting its activities. The primary audience for these dissemination efforts includes providers of health technology solutions and services, as well as researchers who are developing AI tools for healthcare applications. Our main channels for dissemination will be Veracell's website, social media platforms, blog posts, and participation in relevant national health technology and AI events. Veracell has marketing personnel who will assist the project implementation team in reaching dissemination channels. Activities will also involve promoting the CVDLINK website and seeking synergy opportunities with other relevant initiatives and projects that involve Finnish partners.

Our dissemination and communication plan includes sharing news, results, events, and key outcomes with respect to the CVDLINK vision and impact. The content will focus on the topics Veracell contributes to, such as federated repository and techniques enabling providers to connect and share their data, building confidence in AI- and data-driven solutions by disseminating technology updates, AI advancements, tools developed, updates of Platform-as-a-Service, and current state review with respect to regulations and national laws. Before dissemination, the impact of the activities to be disseminated will be evaluated with respect to CVDLINK dissemination strategy and project ambition.

Additionally, we have planned a press release for Deliverable 3.3., which will highlight the final versions of the CVDLINK federated repository and data management tool. Furthermore, Veracell will contribute to research papers related to the tasks in which it is involved.

9.8.9 AMC

AMC intends to 1) communicate the project's results through our professional organisational and communication channels, such as our LinkedIn and our official website which is visited by thousands of users and patients daily, and 2) disseminate our scientific publications in A1/Q1 journals and conferences, such as Nature. However, the exact opportunities we will pursue are not decided yet, and we will follow CVDLINK procedures about notifying the consortium when we've identified specific publication opportunities to pursue. Moreover, we aim to disseminate the results to local news outlets in local languages.

9.8.10 CERTH

CERTH's plans for dissemination and communication activities are below.

Publications: CERTH intends to publish in high-impact journals relevant to the fields of Deep Learning, XAI, and cardiology, targeting at least two publications by the end of the project. We will also explore opportunities for presenting our results at international conferences and symposiums, starting in May 2024.

Media engagement: We will actively engage with local media to share significant milestones and successes of our project.

Social media: To maintain continuous engagement with our community, we will leverage our existing social media platforms (e.g., LinkedIn) to share updates, publications, and interesting facts related to our project and specific task activities.

Website: We will also maintain a section on our institution's website dedicated to the project, providing regular updates, resources, and contact information to facilitate outreach and engagement.

9.8.11 HYMC

HYMC's dissemination plan for CVDLINK targets two primary audiences: the general public in Israel and healthcare and research professionals. To effectively reach these audiences, our project leverages the expertise of HYMC's dedicated PR department. Initially, this department will assist in disseminating the vision, objectives, and importance of CVDLINK. As the project progresses, we will broaden our dissemination efforts to showcase achievements and results. This will include coverage in various media channels such as news outlets and websites tailored for both healthcare professionals and the general public. Additionally, we plan to present our study at relevant national meetings and conferences to further engage with and inform key stakeholders in the healthcare and research communities.

9.8.12 KIHDL

KIHDL plans to create social media posts when the project achieves its milestones and will share and repost publications from partners and the project's LinkedIn page. KIHDL currently has plans to mention the project during presentations about their broader work at scientific conferences next year, and will pursue other scientific presentation and publication opportunities throughout the duration of the project.

9.8.13 UHAM

UHAM's key task in CVDLINK involves federated learning and inference mechanisms. In this task, UHAM aims to leverage existing generic federated machine learning tools from FeatureCloud.ai, focusing on methods that have shown high performance in previous studies involving next-generation sequencing data. The team will assess the performance of FeatureCloud apps that implement popular classification methods such as federated random forest and federated adaptive boosting within the context of CVDLINK. Additionally, they will explore established centralized cardiovascular disease methods and tools, evaluating their effectiveness on centralized test data and investigating the feasibility of transitioning them to a federated approach. Promising approaches will be re-implemented in a federated manner and made available through an app store, complete with documentation and test data.

The following dissemination activities are planned during the project:

Scientific Publications: the project will aim to publish research findings, methodologies, and outcomes in reputable scientific journals related to cardiovascular disease, machine learning, and federated learning. This will ensure that the project's contributions are shared with the scientific community and contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field.

Scientific Conferences: To amplify CVDLINK's impact, UHAM plans to participate in key conferences such as ICLR for machine learning, AHA and ESC Congress for cardiovascular research, and specialized federated learning events. Engaging through workshops, panel discussions, and exhibition booths at these venues will highlight the project's advancements in federated learning and cardiovascular disease research. Additionally, this approach facilitates networking with experts and stakeholders, fostering collaborations and enhancing the visibility of CVDLINK's contributions to the field.

Online Resources: Dissemination through FeatureCloud.ai: Integrating the developed tools and methodologies into the FeatureCloud.ai program and promoting them through the platform will enhance their visibility and accessibility to a broader audience interested in machine learning for cardiovascular disease research. Creating online resources such as video tutorials, documentation, and data repositories will enable broader access to the project's outputs.

Stakeholder Engagement: Engaging with stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, policymakers, and industry representatives through targeted communication efforts.

Presenting the project's outcomes in a format accessible to non-experts will ensure that the potential impact of the research is effectively communicated.

Social Media and Press Releases: Utilizing social media channels and issuing press releases to disseminate project updates, achievements, and relevant news to a wider audience will help raise awareness about the project and its contributions in the field of cardiovascular disease research and machine learning.

By implementing these dissemination strategies, UHAM aims to maximize the impact of CVDLINK's research outcomes, foster collaboration, and contribute to advancements in cardiovascular disease research and machine learning.

9.8.14 UMFCD

As a partner in CVDLINK, "Carol Davila" University of Medicine and Pharmacy from Bucharest, Romania proposes the following dissemination plan:

At a national level, UMFCD is committed to disseminating the project's objectives to stakeholders and key people in the health field who can advocate for the implementation of artificial intelligence as a prevention method for patients with cardiovascular disease. This will be achieved through oral communication and virtual dissemination on the university's official website and social media pages.

From a scientific point of view, UMFCD is committed to participating with the research results at national and international congresses as well as publishing scientific articles in open access ISI medical journals.

Through the dissemination strategy presented above, UMFCD will maximize the impact of the project, increase its visibility, broaden the study base through applied cases, and ensure that the project results reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders and potential users.

9.8.15 IMSP

The primary goal of IMSP Institute of Cardiology is to make the medical community in the Republic of Moldova open towards new medical technologies, including AI. As this is a new field in the country, IMSP will aim to publish research outcomes in national journals, such as Moldovan Medical Journal, as well as international ones. We will attend as many medical events as possible to give presentations and participate in workshops, thus increasing visibility for the CVDLINK project. These will include monthly cardiology conferences, MedEspera, and the Balkan Medical Union. Finally, we will share information on different social media platforms, presenting the project and giving updates relevant to the general and medical community.

9.8.16 WELLICS

Improving people's lives through the seamless interaction with technology and data science is what drives WELLICS. Its scope is to make things simple and meaningful and

create value. The expertise of the WELLICS team is a blend of software engineering, data analytics, health services, and product innovation. Its activities are supported by an extensive network of wellbeing and health experts and leverages years of combined experience in industry and academia. WELLICS products are simple and smart. They provide actionable, personalized insights by integrating data and profiling information through data analytics, mobile applications, and a digital marketplace that seamlessly interact to generate value. WELLICS serves corporates, researchers, and well-being and health experts. Most importantly, WELLICS serves everyone who takes quality of life seriously and wants a personal digital coach with them at all times.

During the project, WELLICS will explore its developed network of contacts in order to disseminate the results of CVDLINK, focusing on establishing a link between the innovations related to cardiovascular disease management and the corporate wellbeing dimension, WELLICS' core commercial activity. In addition, the activities, achievements, and main results of the project will be communicated through the company's social media accounts (especially X and LinkedIn) as well as the personal social media accounts of the people working in the project. Last but not least, WELLICS is in the process of developing a dedicated website (based on HubSpot) functioning as a central dissemination node, where the main outcomes and achievements of all the company's research and innovation activities (including CVDLINK) will be presented in detail.

9.8.17 KTU

KTU will disseminate CVDLINK activities and achievements to two types of audiences: professionals, such as research stakeholders, and the public, including citizens, patients, and patient associations. KTU plans to present CVDLINK project-related results at conferences such as Computing in Cardiology (CinC'2025) and the IEEE-EMBS International Conference on Biomedical and Health Informatics (BHI'2026). The first conference is a prestigious event held annually since 1974, attracting scientists and professionals from the fields of medicine, physics, engineering, and computer science. KTU will initiate a collaborative effort to prepare and present preliminary Clinical Study 3 related results, for example, assessment of the risk of heart arrhythmia by biophysics-guided machine learning algorithms using non-invasive electrolyte disbalance monitoring, semiautomatic annotation of medical data, and federated learning for enhanced bio signal-based digital biomarker estimation with privacy awareness in CinC'2025 and BHI'2026 respectively. Preliminary results will be extended, and at least two journal papers will be initiated, prepared, and submitted to open access journals such as CSBJ: Smart Hospital (impact factor 9.1, publisher Elsevier), and IEEE Biomedical and Health Informatics (impact factor 7.7, publisher IEEE). Representatives from both academic and industrial partners will be invited to contribute to the efforts described above.

KTU has a dedicated Department of Marketing and Communications, which will assist the project implementation team in reaching dissemination channels such as national electronic news outlets like www.lrt.lt, www.delfi.lt, and www.lrytas.lt, as well as more specialized health-related web portals such as www.sveikata.lt and international health-

related electronic web portals like www.ScienceDaily.com. For the news outlets, we plan to prepare and disseminate public-oriented versions of each published conference and journal paper. The main findings and project developments will be translated into plain language understandable to the general population.

9.8.18 UTARTU

The outcomes of the CVDLINK project and UTARTU's contributions will be disseminated through Open Access publications. Moreover, these findings will be presented in routine internal seminars and, when applicable, at local and international scientific conferences.

UTARTU will promote the scientific outputs they are involved in by summarising and communicating them to broad audiences via various media channels, including press releases distributed to popular science platforms such as <https://novaator.err.ee/>. Additionally, social media accounts linked to the Institute of Genomics at the University of Tartu will be utilized to amplify outreach efforts. All communication activities will be conducted in close collaboration with communication specialists from the Institute of Genomics.

9.8.19 SYNYO GmbH

SYNYO GmbH will contribute to the dissemination and communication activities through the development of online graphic design materials (e.g., images, brochures, factsheets) and by promoting the project through its own network of healthcare and technology partners. Additionally, SYNYO will share the project materials and posts through its healthcare researchers' and impact managers' profiles to expand the reach of the project, and potentially facilitate the networking with other relevant EU projects. Lastly, SYNYO will look for opportunities to disseminate content within the scientific community either proactively, or by contributing to other partners' activities.

CVDLINK Project Consortium

 TUDa						
 UMFCD						
	 SYNYO					